

Bromination of *p*-Nitrophenol in Acetic Acid—Inhibition by Hydrogen Bromide

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Bromination of *p*-nitrophenol (ArH) in acetic acid follows the rate expression

$$\text{Rate} = k[\text{ArH}][\text{Br}_2] + k'[\text{ArH}][\text{Br}_2]^{1/2} + k''[\text{ArH}]^2[\text{Br}_2].$$

Hydrogen bromide reduces the concentrations of ArH and bromine available for the reaction by complexing with them. However, this is not the only cause of inhibition. The extent of inhibition of hydrogen bromide is also determined by the nature and reactivity of the substrate. The general mechanism for aromatic bromination holds good even in the presence of hydrogen bromide.

BROMINATION of aromatic substrates (ArH) by molecular bromine in acetic acid usually takes place through parallel paths and the rate may be expressed as

$$\text{Rate} = k[\text{ArH}][\text{Br}_2] + k'[\text{ArH}][\text{Br}_2]^2 \quad \dots (1)$$

the overall orders being dependent on the relative concentrations of the substrate and bromine^{1,2}. The postulated mechanism involves the interaction of an electrophile with a 1:1 complex between substrate and bromine in the rate determining step, the electrophile being bromine itself in the third order process and the solvent in the second order process^{2,3}. The variable orders in bromine as well as in ArH, observed in the bromination of *p*-nitrophenol, have been explained by a mechanism involving *p*-nitrophenol as an electrophile in the rate determining step⁴. The inhibition observed in the bromination of aromatic substrates in acetic acid has been attributed to HBr which fixes the bromine as HBr₃⁵ or ArH as ArH·HBr⁶. To verify these possibilities, a detailed study of the effect of hydrogen bromide on the bromination of *p*-nitrophenol in acetic acid has been made.

Experimental

Glacial acetic acid (GR SM) was purified according to Orton's procedure and its purity ascertained by determining the freezing point. KMnO₄ was used instead of CrO₃⁷. Bromine (AR BDH ampoules) was used without further purification. *p*-Nitrophenol was recrystallised from 2% hydrochloric acid. Hydrogen bromide gas prepared by the dropwise addition of bromine to dry tetralin was bubbled through glacial acetic acid, till saturation. The concentration of hydrogen bromide was ascertained by Volhard's method⁸.

Rate measurements:

The kinetics of the reaction was followed iodometrically by determining the concentration of bromine as a function of time, at 30°. The reactions were carried out by the batch method⁹. The orders have been determined by the isolation method using the initial rates. The procedure minimises the influence of the products formed during the reaction. The slopes at various concentrations were taken from concentration-time curves by the mirror method¹⁰ and the initial rates obtained from the double logarithmic plots of rate versus concentration.

Results and Discussion

The individual orders with respect to the reactants at various concentrations are reported in Tables 1 to 3. The [Br₂]_T to [ArH]_T ratios in Table 1 (a, b, d, e, g & h) are relatively lower than those in Table 2 (a, b, d, e & f). At low [Br₂]_T/[ArH]_T, the orders in Br₂ and ArH are one and two respectively while the order in HBr varies from 0 to -1. At high [Br₂]_T/[ArH]_T, the orders in Br₂ and ArH are two and one respectively, while that in HBr is again variable. That the ratios of concentrations rather than the individual concentrations are more significant, has been shown by working at lower concentrations of the reactants but maintaining a lower [Br₂]_T/[ArH]_T (Table 2, f & g). The order in bromine is then reduced to a lower value. At some intermediate concentrations of the reactants (Table 3, a & b), the order in ArH is less than two and bromine greater than one. The order in hydrogen bromide determined under these conditions is -1 (Table 3, c).

The existence of variable orders in substrate and bromine could be qualitatively explained on the basis of the general mechanism³. In the presence of HBr, the formation of HBr₃ decreases the [free Br₂] to such an extent that at low [Br₂]_T/[ArH]_T, the sub-

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TABLE I—ORDERS AND RATE CONSTANTS IN THE BROMINATION OF *p*-NITROPHENOL IN THE PRESENCE OF HYDROGEN BROMIDE AT LOW $[\text{Br}_2]/[\text{ArH}]$

Solvent : HOAc

Temperature : 30°

No.	Concentration (mole lit ⁻¹)						Orders in reactants	Rate constants (lit ² mole ⁻² min ⁻¹)					
	[ArH] × 10 ³		[Br ₂] × 10 ²		[HBr] × 10 ²			10 ³ k _h	10 ³ k _h '				
	Total	Free	Total	Free	Total	Free							
<i>a</i>	45.30	42.27	2.40	0.84	3.03	1.48	2.03 (ArH) _T	18.8	21.5				
	30.00	26.97						19.1	23.6				
	20.00	16.97						1.80 (ArH) _F	24.8	29.2			
<i>b</i>	42.86	39.83	2.40	0.84	3.03	1.48	1.20 (Br ₂) _T	18.7	21.6				
			1.52	0.44				1.95	20.4	23.7			
			0.99	0.26				2.29	1.00 (Br ₂) _F	21.7	25.1		
			0.48	0.11				2.70	19.8	22.9			
<i>c</i>	42.86	37.01	0.92	0.12	5.85	5.06	-1.00 (HBr) _T	22.6	30.2				
		38.39						0.16	4.47	3.72	22.2	27.6	
		39.38						0.21	3.48	2.77	-0.85 (HBr) _F	22.9	27.1
		40.76						0.32	2.11	1.51	26.5	29.4	
<i>d</i>	40.00	38.44	2.42	1.42	1.56	0.56	1.80 (ArH) _T	27.1	29.4				
		30.00						28.44	29.7	33.1			
		25.00						23.44	1.75 (ArH) _F	32.5	37.0		
<i>e</i>	42.79	41.17	2.53	1.44	1.62	0.61	1.05 (Br ₂) _T	27.4	29.7				
			1.89	0.99				0.72	28.9	31.2			
			0.95	0.40				1.10	0.85 (Br ₂) _F	33.9	36.7		
<i>f</i>	42.70	40.64	2.68	1.38	2.06	0.76	-0.32 (HBr) _T	28.9	31.9				
		41.15		1.64		1.55		0.51	27.2	30.0			
		41.54		1.87		1.16		0.25	-0.27 (HBr) _F	29.4	31.1		
		42.18		2.30		0.52		0.15	27.4	28.2			
<i>g</i> *	42.60	42.40	2.16	1.96	0.20	—	2.00 (ArH) _T	38.7	—				
		25.00						24.80	37.3	—			
		20.00						19.80	43.1	—			
<i>h</i> *	45.00	44.90	2.44	2.34	0.10	—	1.03 (Br ₂) _T	38.4	—				
			1.66	1.56				41.7	—				
			1.20	1.10				40.9	—				
<i>i</i> *	45.00	44.75	2.45	2.20	0.25	—	0.00 (HBr) _T	37.3	—				
		44.85		2.30				0.15	40.7	—			
		44.90		2.35				0.10	38.8	—			

* Since the hydrogen bromide concentration is very low $[\text{Br}_2]_F$ is obtained by subtracting $[\text{HBr}]_T$ from $[\text{Br}_2]_T$. Here $[\text{ArH}]_T \approx [\text{ArH}]_F$ and $[\text{Br}_2]_T \approx [\text{Br}_2]$. Hence the free orders in $[\text{ArH}]$ and $[\text{Br}_2]$ will be the same as the total orders in ArH and Br₂. Rate constant for the uninhibited process⁴ = 31.2×10^{-5} lit² mole⁻² min⁻¹.

trate acts as the electrophile. At high $[\text{Br}_2]_T/[\text{ArH}]_T$, the concentration of free bromine, may be sufficiently high to enable it to act as the electrophile. A second order in bromine can be satisfactorily explained by assuming bromine to act as an electrophile rather than as a base since one could expect bromine to be a weaker base than ArH. A change in mechanism is less likely to occur just by varying $[\text{Br}_2]_T/[\text{ArH}]_T$. A mechanism implying the involvement of a second molecule of ArH as a base assisting in the proton removal step is less likely since an inverse dependence of rate on bromide ion concentration is not observed.

A more detailed analysis of the experimental results is attempted by considering the following equilibria in acetic acid

TABLE 2—ORDERS AND RATE CONSTANTS IN THE BROMINATION OF *p*-NITROPHENOL IN THE PRESENCE OF HYDROGEN BROMIDE AT HIGH $[Br_2]/[ArH]$

Solvent : HOAc		Concentration (mole lit ⁻¹)					Orders in reactants		Rate constants (lit ² mole ⁻² min ⁻¹)					
No.	$[ArH] \times 10^2$		$[Br_2] \times 10^2$		$[HBr] \times 10^2$				$10^3 k_1$	$10^3 k'$				
	Total	Free	Total	Free	Total	Free								
<i>a</i> *	43.20	40.10	8.05	5.36	3.10	0.40	1.20 (ArH) _T							
	30.00	26.90												
	20.00	16.90												
	10.00	6.90												
<i>b</i> *	43.20	40.10	8.05	5.30	3.10	0.40	2.10 (Br ₂) _T							
											6.87	4.26		0.49
											5.95	3.44		0.59
											4.98	2.62		0.72
<i>c</i> *	43.10	37.80	7.13	2.07	5.30	1.12	-1.12 (HBr) _T							
		39.90										3.74		0.70
		40.10										4.58		0.45
		41.00										5.40		0.27
<i>d</i> *	43.20	41.18	7.13	5.39	2.02	0.26	1.00 (ArH) _T							
	30.00	27.98												
	20.00	17.98												
	10.00	7.98												
<i>e</i>	15.00	13.57	2.53	1.59	1.43	0.48	1.13 (ArH) _T		69.3	76.4				
	10.00	9.57												
	5.00	3.57												0.90 (ArH) _F
<i>f</i>	20.00	18.57	4.08	2.95	1.43	0.31	2.13 (Br ₂) _T		54.9	59.1				
											3.00	1.99		0.41
											2.00	1.16		0.57
<i>g</i> *	20.00	18.57	1.01	0.48	1.43	0.90	1.70 (Br ₂) _T							
											0.74	0.32		1.02
											0.49	0.20		1.14
											0.22	0.09		1.29
<i>h</i>	20.00	17.98	3.28	1.88	2.02	0.60	-0.46 (HBr) _T		56.4	62.8				
		18.57										2.19		1.49
		19.17										2.58		0.83
		19.64										3.00		0.36
									0.40	59.2				
									0.22	49.3				
									0.08	51.7				

* Rate constants for *a*, *b*, *c*, *d* and *g* have not been evaluated because of the fractional orders in bromine. Rate constant for the uninhibited process⁴ = 100.4 lit² mole⁻² min⁻¹.

TABLE 3—ORDERS IN THE BROMINATION OF *p*-NITROPHENOL IN THE PRESENCE OF HYDROGEN BROMIDE AT INTERMEDIATE $[Br_2]/[ArH]$

Solvent : HOAc		Concentration (mole lit ⁻¹)					Orders in reactants					
No.	$[ArH] \times 10^2$		$[Br_2] \times 10^2$		$[HBr] \times 10^2$							
	Total	Free	Total	Free	Total	Free						
<i>a</i> *	45.30	42.96	3.25	1.62	2.34	0.76	1.40 (ArH) _T					
	30.00	29.70										
	20.00	17.70										
	10.00	7.66										
<i>b</i> *	45.30	42.96	3.25	1.62	2.34	0.76	1.40 (Br ₂) _T					
									2.16	0.91		1.09
									1.06	0.35		1.62
									0.55			1.95
<i>c</i> *	42.80	38.57	3.33	0.99	4.23	1.89	-1.15 (HBr) _T					
		39.53								1.31		3.27
		40.48								1.74		2.32
												0.73

* The rate constants have not been evaluated because of the fractional order in ArH.

The value of K_1 as determined by Kolthoff *et al.*¹¹ is very low. ($K_1 = 10^{-5}$ to 10^{-6}). Spectral studies in the visible region on mixtures of *p*-nitrophenol and hydrogen bromide in acetic acid indicated a very weak absorption band around 470 $m\mu$. The extinction coefficient (ϵ) and equilibrium constant (K_2) were evaluated from the Scott equation¹² by the method of least squares, as 250 and 8.59×10^{-2} lit. mole⁻¹ respectively. Hence the equilibria corresponding to the dissociation of hydrogen bromide in acetic acid¹¹ and the formation of the $ArH \cdot HBr$ complex may be neglected in comparison with the formation of HBr_3 ¹³ ($K_3 = 125$). The concentrations of free hydrogen bromide and free bromine in the various concentration regions can therefore be evaluated using K_3 as follows :

$$[HBr]_T = [HBr]_F + [HBr_3] \quad \dots (5)$$

$$[Br_2]_F = [Br_2]_T / 1 + K_3 [HBr]_F \quad \dots (6)$$

The concentration of free hydrogen bromide is given as

$$[HBr]_F = -b \pm (b^2 - 4ac)^{1/2} / 2a \quad \dots (7)$$

where $b = (1 + K_3 [Br_2]_T - K_3 [HBr]_T)$

$$a = K_3$$

and $c = -[HBr]_T$.

The concentration of free ArH is calculated by assuming that hydrogen bromide present, both as free hydrogen bromide and as HBr_3 , complexes with ArH thereby reducing the $[ArH]$ available for the reaction

$$\text{i.e., } [ArH]_F = [ArH]_T - [HBr]_T \quad \dots (8)$$

where $[HBr]_T = [HBr]_F + [HBr_3]$.

The orders in "free Br_2 " and "free ArH " have been included in Tables 1, 2 and 3. The orders for the total and free concentrations are not very much different except for the results in Table 2(b).

The rate constants k_h , k'_h , k_1 and k'_1 , evaluated by considering both $[ArH]_T$ and $[ArH]_F$ for the various concentration ranges using the expressions

$$\text{Rate} = k_h [ArH]_T^2 [Br_2]_F \quad \dots (9)$$

$$\text{Rate} = k_1 [ArH]_T [Br_2]_F^2 \quad \dots (10)$$

$$\text{Rate} = k'_h [ArH]_F^2 [Br_2]_F \quad \dots (11)$$

and

$$\text{Rate} = k_1 [ArH]_F [Br_2]_F^2 \quad \dots (12)$$

are tabulated in Tables 1 and 2.

The values of the rate constants k_h and k'_h (Table 1) are lower at higher concentration of hydrogen bromide (approximately $6.0 \times 10^{-2} M$ to $2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$)

than the values at lower concentrations of hydrogen bromide (approximately $2.0 \times 10^{-2} M$ to $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$). The rate constants thus calculated for the experiments with lower concentrations of hydrogen bromide are in better agreement with the rate constants for the bromination of *p*-nitrophenol in the absence of hydrogen bromide, when the orders are two in *p*-nitrophenol and one in bromine. The rate constants k_1 and k'_1 (Table 2) are lower than the ones obtained for the bromination of *p*-nitrophenol without added hydrogen bromide. This means that at higher concentrations of hydrogen bromide, the correction applied is not satisfactory suggesting that some other factor is involved which reduces the rate further.

Since bromination of aromatic compounds in polar solvents is considered to proceed through a polar transition state, an increase in the dielectric constant of the medium can enhance the rate of such a reaction. Dielectric constants of solutions of *p*-nitrophenol, hydrogen bromide and bromine in acetic acid were measured with a DK meter 60 GK consisting of a cell plated with platinum (Table 4).

It is seen that the dielectric constant of the medium increases with an increase in the concentration of either *p*-nitrophenyl or hydrogen bromide in acetic acid but does not change with the concentration of bromine. Lower values of rates at higher $[HBr]$ point to the possibility that one molecule of hydrogen bromide may deactivate more than one molecule of substrate.¹⁴

In the case of a less complicated substrate like mesitylene, the inhibition in the presence of hydrogen bromide can be accounted for entirely in terms of the reduction in the concentration of free bromine due to the formation of HBr_3 .¹⁵

TABLE 4—DIELECTRIC CONSTANTS OF HYDROGEN BROMIDE AND *p*-NITROPHENOL IN ANHYDROUS ACETIC ACID

SOLVENT : HOAc		Temperature : 30°	
$[HBr] \times 10^2$ mole lit ⁻¹)	<i>D</i>	$[p\text{-nitrophenol}]$ $\times 10^2$ (mole lit ⁻¹)	<i>D</i>
6.00	10.7	43.00	8.3
4.00	9.4	30.10	7.4
1.90	7.8	20.20	6.6
1.10	6.8	9.90	6.5

This supports the view that the structure and reactivity of the substrate determines the extra inhibition observed in the presence of added hydrogen bromide.

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